

HBO + MBO good contribution to open education

Learn from HBO about citizen science, how they structure it, etc.

Sharing technical infrastructure across institutions

Cultural integration into Dutch society

Shared open days

Practical knowledge opening up the working field

Dialogue with other knowledge systems/craftmanship

More inclusive approach to OS since broader group of society

Practical, hands on mentality

Scientific insights

Implementation knowledge

How to put policy into practice (top > down)

Loss of specific types of knowledge & learning - practical experiences in the field, different perspectives

Practical solutions

Small % of population went to university/HBO, majority went elsewhere

Build a network of different professions

Educational materials

Is research been done in MBO?

Facilities on campus. Sharing economics

Cooperation understanding

Contribution of large group

Cross over knowledge exchange

Start young via public engagement to primary schools/MBOs

Transfer of knowledge doesn't take place efficiently

Distance to society grows when MBO is excluded

Adding perspectives!

Miss out on half the research

Communication with non academics is missing

- Open Software
- Open Methods
- Open Hardware

Miss connection with applied technical sciences and professional organisations

Funding calls for combined WO/HBO/MBO projects (or even MBO/HBO)

Promote more and discuss at open science festival

Trust in institutions

More difficult to connect to society

Include MBO/HBO in OSCs

Q2

What practical steps can we take to build Open Science infrastructures that recognize applied, community-driven research?

*overlap driven by digital communication between stakeholders

samenwerking in onderzoek vanuit onderwijs stimuleren

platform where people can find each other

training modules on skills for everyone

ensuring sufficient resources (financial funding)

bringing together the MBO network (administrative)

scientific language -> how do we talk about science/research (language)

citizen science projects that incorporate knowledge from each institution

mbo/hbo "in the lead"

involve public libraries.

What practical steps can we take to build Open Science infrastructures that recognize applied, community-driven research?

Structuring metadata in communication to drive research + your discovery system is clear that it is this

Poblinova -> Marketing Campaign?

Include MBO/HBO in NWO calls

Broadening network (outside of university) for PR + Marketing (story telling)

Mapping existing solutions -> knowledge bank of solutions

Commonly knows research utilization (i.e. bird count) -> publishing the data.

Social Infrastructure

Understanding what we mean by infrastructure

Weaving these data into the format of selected infrastructure

Funding for the entire project (Beethoven)

buildings closer together vocational education on the (university) campus

Student recruitment based on key themes

sharing facilities
-> if infrastructure already exists, find each other, work together and use each other

Making lifelong learning accessible for higher professional education /vocational education